

Experimenting Domain Title Service to Meet Mobility and Multicast Aggregation by using OpenFlow

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Abstract. *Researchers from all over the world are engaged in the design of a new Internet, from the ground up. As it happened in the dawn of the current Internet, this new development is experimentally oriented and much of it has been happening in large test beds. At this time, our own efforts are concentrated on developing a new naming and addressing scheme for the future Internet. Here we propose to use the OFELIA test bed and OpenFlow as an enabling infrastructure, in order to extend the experiments we are already performing regarding to the DTS (Domain Title Service) exploring its contributions on mobility and multicast aggregation.*

1. Introduction

The basic principles of the Internet were set at the beginning of the seventies [Cerf and Kahn 1974] and their development was based on a experimental research using the ARPANET [Catlett and Toole 1998].

If in one hand the stability of these protocols lead to the dissemination of the Internet, at the other hand this now refrains its modernization [De Souza Pereira et al. 2010]. This dissemination lead to a new set of requirements that are not satisfied by these protocols. For example, the need of security, privacy, quality of service, better handling of peer-to-peer applications, support for sensors and smart phones with its mobility, real time produced contents such as voice and video. Besides this technical aspects, in a totally new scenario, the requirements comprises aspects as energy consumption, social and economic needs as exposed by [Tselentis et al. 2009].

Researchers from all over the world are engaged in the design of a new Internet, from the ground up. This so *clean slate* frees the research from the legacy of the current architecture and fosters innovations [Roberts 2009]. At a future time, when results should be deployed, the research will then be refocused to the transition from the current Internet to the future Internet.

The future Internet is evolving in a experimental way and much of this research happens in test beds such as: PLANETLAB [Peterson and Roscoe 2006]; GENI (Global Environment for Network Innovations) [Elliott 2010]; and initiatives like FIRE (Future

Internet Research & Experimentation) [Gavras et al. 2007], that congregates different test beds with specific purposes, as ONELAB [Onelab 2011] and OFELIA [OFELIA 2011].

OpenFlow [McKeown et al. 2008] is a product of this *Clean Slate* approach. Its basic goal is to enable researchers to innovate in the computer science field related to networking and communication. Essentially, OpenFlow separates the data plane from the control plane, defining an OpenFlow switch. An OpenFlow compatible switch offers a common interface where the controller can modify the switch behavior at run time using the OpenFlow protocol. The main vendors are enabling OpenFlow in their products, thus, fostering its use by the academy and the industry.

OpenFlow can enable the development of new naming, addressing and routing schemes and this can be accomplished using different approaches such as SCAFFOLD [Freedman et al. 2010] and the Framework for Internet Innovation (FII) [Koponen et al. 2011] that could allow different architectures to coexist, communicate, and evolve. The freedom to experiment, interoperate and innovate empowers the research community to pave the way to the future Internet.

Since 2009 our research group has been working and modelling concepts related to the future Internet and the Title Model ontology, published at the FIA (Future Internet Assembly) book [Pereira et al. 2011] aggregates these key concepts. The main goal of this proposal is to scale the experiments regarding to the DTS (Domain Title Service) exploring its contributions on mobility and multicast aggregation.

The DTS [de Souza Pereira et al. 2010] consists of a distributed system over the network elements responsible for maintaining the entity titles available in that domain and their communication requirements over time.

The title is a designation to ensure an unambiguous identification of an entity. One title designates only one entity, but one entity can have more than a title. The title plays a key role in order to provide the horizontal addressing of the entities.

An Entity is a thing which has communication requirements that can be semantically understood from top to bottom layers. Some examples: a content; a service; a device, sensor, pad, or smart phone; a user; an application; a system; a process. The entity has some titles, requirements and a variable location over time.

Composed by DTSA (Domain Title Service Agents), DTS plays an important role at central aspects of networking like naming and addressing and has the ability to share the context among communicating entities.

This sharing is provided by the workspace. The workspace is a logical bus which has a title and contains network elements required to support the communication of the entities. The workspace is created by an entity willing to communicate with a specific purpose and thus defines its requirements and capabilities. A new entity can be joined to a existing workspace and in such event, the logical bus can be extended to handle its communication.

In the same way, an entity can move through the DTS being capable to keep it communicating. The main concept introduced by the workspace is that the destination address is its title. Another important concept introduced by the workspace is that the primitive, for example a stream, is sent once by the source and can be received by all the

Figure 1. DTS and OpenFlow

entities sharing it.

Over the network, DTSA are distributed on that domain being deployed at servers and network elements (switches, routers and so on) as shown on Figure 1.

A DTSA is implemented as an OpenFlow Controller. Based on this approach, each network will have a DSTA responsible for the configuration of network elements based on the communication requirements.

The remainder of this proposal is organized as follows: Section 2 details the objectives of the experiments; Section 3 describes the project; and Section 4 exposes the expected results.

2. Objectives

To accomplish overall goal of this proposal, the following objectives are presented:

- Scale two categories of traffic intensive experiments, one based on the Title Model for future Internet using an extended OpenFlow controller and the other based on IPv6 comparing their performance and scalability using different parameters like latency and throughput;
- Experiments a new naming scheme based on titles and implements the horizontal address, validating the deploy of this approach using OpenFlow based switches regarding mobility and multicast aggregation;
- Compare the performance of IPv6 multicast with the multicast supported by the DTS;
- Foster collaboration with other research groups.

3. Project Description

Considering that the Test Bed must have OpenFlow deployed in its infrastructure, OFE-LIA is the right choice the conduct the experimental research proposed.

Figure 2 shows a possible deploy necessary to conduct the experiments. Initially will be used the island of i2CAT (Barcelona) in order to conduct the first phase of experiments. The second phase, will consider the communication between the islands located

at i2CAT (Barcelona) and UEssex (Essex), in order to verify and measure the behavior within long distances and with unpredicted traffic using the infrastructure.

During the experiments the number of hosts and the instances of applications running will be scaled. One category of experiments will run using the TCP/IP protocol stack based on IPv6 and the other, using our communication approach, will use a special socket that is not based at the TCP/IP protocol stack.

In this case, the communication between the applications will be based only in their title, which in this case, will be a single description of it. Another entity that will be present is the workspace and its title will be mapped on a VLAN identifier.

The workspace title, plus the ingress port at the switch will be used to construct the flow table and in this case the action associated will be the output ports that will receive the frames.

The flow tables will be modified by the DTSA, according to the request made by the entities. In this case, the control plane will be modified considering the requirements presented by the entities to the DTS.

The addressing mode used will not be based at the MAC address, but in the title.

The DTSA will handle the messages and will modify the flow tables accordingly connecting the applications and modifying the data plane in order to provide unicast and multicast.

Figure 2. Deployment at OFELIA Facilities

3.1. Schedule

The work breakdown structure of the project and the schedule is presented at figure 3. Before handling the experiments, an Elaboration phase (WP1) will be executed. Under this phase the set up of the accounts and the project will be created under OFELIA facility and a manual for conducting the experiments will be produced to be used by the team.

3.2. Team

Coordinated by experienced researchers and with a group of young PhDs and motivated students the team is leading a new vision of the future Internet networks. The team engaged in this proposal is composed by five PhDs from FACOM (UFU) and two other PhDs

TASK NAME	DURATION	START	FINISH
Kick-off Meeting- Poznan - Future Internet Week	1 day	10/2011	10/2011
Planning Experiments with OFELIA	2 days	10/2011	10/2011
WP1 - Elaboration	2.75 mons	11/2011	01/2012
WP2 - Phase One - Experiments at i2CAT	4.5 mons	01/2012	05/2012
WP3 - Phase Two - Experiments at i2CAT interconnected with UEssex	4.5 mons	05/2012	09/2012
WP4 - Results Publications and Dissemination	2 mons	09/2012	11/2012
WP5 - Project Management	14 mons	10/2011	11/2012

Figure 3. Planned WBS and Schedule

from LSI (USP). Moreover, the group from FACOM will have four graduate students and two PhD students from LSI (USP), as shown below:

- UFU - FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF UBERLÂNDIA
 - Prof. Dr. Pedro Frosi Rosa (**Coordinator**)
 - Prof. Dr. Lásaro Jonas Camargos
 - Prof. Dr. Rafael Pasquini
 - Prof. Dr. Michel dos Santos Soares
 - Prof. Dr. Luís Fernando Faina
 - Prof. M.Sc. Paulo Rodolfo da Silva Leite Coelho
 - Acrísio José do Nascimento Jr. - M.Sc. student
 - Lucas Clemente Vella - M.Sc. student
 - Emílio Carvalho Dias - M.Sc. student
 - Maurício Amaral Gonçalves - M.Sc. student
- USP - UNIVERSITY OF SÃO PAULO
 - Prof. Dr. Sérgio Takeo Kofuji
 - Prof. Dr. Volnys Borges Bernal
 - Prof. M.Sc. Flávio de Oliveira Silva - Ph.D. student
 - M.Sc. João Henrique de Souza Pereira - Ph.D. student

4. Expected Results

Using OpenFlow as an enabling infrastructure, the experimental research conducted will demonstrate a new naming and addressing scheme that will enable seamless mobility and multicast aggregation. The results might show a viable approach for handling communications based on a horizontal addressing, which can be an enabling technology for future Internet.

The experiments will provide a rich information that will be used by our research group to conduct the next developments and the future research.

Finally, this work will foster collaboration of other research group with other related groups and will be an important opportunity to share knowledge and experiences.

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